

Benefits of Digital Economy: Special Reference to Digital India

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Abstract:

Prime Minister of India Mr. Narendra Modi on 1 July 2015 announced the Digital India Programme with an objective of connecting rural areas with high-speed internet networks and improving digital literacy. Digital illiteracy, poor infrastructure, low internet speed, diversity of government departments, issue pertaining to taxation etc are hurdles to implement Digital Economy and making Digital India. The vision of this programme is to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. It is one of the biggest steps by government of India

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Introduction:

'The Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence' by author Don Tapscott in 1995 first coin the term of Digital Economy. Digital economy based on digital computing technologies, conducting business through markets based on the internet and the World Wide Web. The digital economy is also referred to as the Internet Economy, New Economy or Web Economy. By e-business, e-business infrastructure and e-commerce these three components are used to influence the consumers by social websites (Facebook, Twitter, Youtube, Instagram). It creates opportunities in healthcare, education, banking sector, entertainment etc. Google, Apple, Microsoft, Amazon are the biggest companies contribute in the digital economy of world. Use of the Internet, **rise in E-Commerce, Digital Goods and Services, Transparency are features of Digital economy.** Challenges of Digital Economy creates **Loss in Employment, Lack of Experts, Heavy Investments.**

In present study we discuss the impact of Digital economy on Digital India. Global digitalisation and future scope in India.

Literature Review:

- [1] Midha (2016) concluded that digital India, bright future but its improper implementation, inaccessibility and inflexibility it leads to failure. By Digital Economy Indians should work together to shape the knowledge economy leads India in digital world.

- [2] Gupta and Arora (2015) studied the impact of digital India project on India's rural sector. It leads to empowerment of women as well as equal opportunity to participate in global economy.
- [3] 'Growth of Digital Economy: A Challenge For Competition Regulators' by Vivekanand Jha conclude in details that how to policy makers should implement the policy and how to work on infrastructures improvements. Generally rural and Urban area is influenced tremendously by this digital Economy as well as Digital India.

Research Methodology:

The paper is based on the secondary data and the information is collected by the internet via journals, research papers and expert opinions on the same subject matter.

Objectives of the Paper:

1. To study the concept of digital India programme and contribution of India.
2. To find out the importance of this programme.
3. To find out the challenges faced in implementation of this programme in India.

Digital India:

A programme to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. 'Digital India is a central programme to make India ready for a knowledge-based future. Programme is based on following keys:

1. Digital Infrastructure as a Utility to Every Citizen:

In Digital Visionary areas are access High speed internet, every citizen has Unique digital identity with Mobile phone & bank account. Facility to every citizen by Common Services Centre, Private space on Cloud and Secure cyber-space. Access high speed Internet connectivity as a core utility for delivery of services to citizens. Digital identity that will be, lifelong, online and authentic able to every citizen. Governance and Services on Demand

Integration across all diverse departments or jurisdictions together for facility of Citizen. For all citizens it should be ensured availability of services in real-time from online & mobile platforms. To make all citizen entitlements portable and available on the cloud make facility to digitally transformed services for improving ease of doing business Leveraging Geo spatial Information Systems (GIS) for decision support systems & development.

2. Digital Empowerment of Citizens :

To empower citizen through universal digital literacy by providing universal accessible digital resource. Available digital resources / services must be in Indian languages. Collaborative digital platforms for participative Governance and Citizens not required to physically submit Government documents / certificates reduce the paper work. Digital literacy, Digital resources, Indian languages, Collaborative digital platforms No physical submission of documents will empower the citizens in Digital Economy

❖ **Basic Pillars of Digital economy are as follows :**

1. **Broadband Highways:**

The aim is to cover 2,50,500 village Panchayats under National Optical Fibre Network (NOFN) by December 2025. Nationwide internet infrastructure (NII) would integrate the network and cloud infrastructure in the country to provide high speed connectivity and cloud platform to various government departments up to the panchayat level.

2. **Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity:**

The aim is to increase network penetration and to provide mobile connectivity to 44000 villages by 2025 with investment of RS 16000 Cr. The Smart phones used by (3.3 billion / 42.63% of world populations), Mobile devices (5.15 billion/ 66.60% of the world population) and Mobile connectivity (7.74 billion population of world have 9.3 billion mobile connections with 5.1 billion are unique mobile connectivity subscriber)

3. **Public Internet Access Programme:**

One Common Service Centre(CSC) would be provided to each gram panchayat and 1,50,000 Post Offices are proposed to be converted into multi service centres.CSCs are the service delivery points enabled with Information and Communication Technology (ICT) for the delivery of various public and private services to rural citizens of India. Presently there are total 2,55,798 active CSC Id's and 687 districts having CSCs across the country. Nearly Rs. 1,200 crore income received by CSCs. Services provided under these centres are Voter ID card, Bill payments, Aadhar, PAN cards, Online tickets, Land records, Tele medicines, Digital literacy etc. New Initiatives are IGNOU Services andWi-Fi Hotspots in villages.

4. **e-Governance:**

IT would be used to make the delivery of government services more effectively. There would be integration of services and platform-UIDAI,Payment Gateway, Mobile Seva platform, Public redressal etc. through IT. All information would be available in electronic form. It will helpful for

paperless and fast communication and implementations.

5. e-Kranti:

The aim is electronic delivery of services to people be it education, health, financial inclusion or justice.

6. Information for All:

My Governmentin is a website launched by the government to facilitate a 2-way communication between citizens and the government. Exchange ideas or suggestion with government through this. Open access to information through open digital data platform to every citizen any time at any time.

7. Electronics Manufacturing:

The main target of Government Zero imports of electronics by 2027,local manufacturing of items fabrications of smart energy meters, micro ATMs, mobile, consumer and medical electronics. Promoting manufacturing and investment in electronics sector by providing clarity on taxation, incentives skill development etc.It is observed that 115 new Mobile manufacturing units started in last 3 years. And 1 lakh direct and 3 lakhs indirect Jobs created.

8. IT for Jobs:

Approximate 10 million people in towns and villages for IT sector jobs available in five years therefore training to 3 lakh service delivery agents as part of skill development to run viable businesses delivering IT services.

9. Early Harvesting Programmes:

Government plans to installed Wi-Fi facilities in all universities across the country log with books will be converted into e-books. Email will be made the primary mode of communication within government. Bio metric Attendance System will be installed make compulsory in all central/ state government / private offices where recording of attendance will be made online.

Bharat Net. (Bharat Broadband Network Limited) is a telecom infrastructure set up provided by the Department of Telecommunications for the establishment, management, and operation of the National Optical Fibre Network to provide a minimum of 100 Mbps broadband connectivity to all 2,50,500 gram panchayats in the country, covering nearly 6,25,000 villages, to improve telecommunications in India and reach the campaign goal of Digital India.The number of internet users in India has registered an annual growth of 8 percent and is estimated at 958 million as of January 2026, a 65.89 percent overall internet penetration, it observed. According to a survey by e-Marketer in India is estimated to have over 1.3 billion internet users in 2030.

Benefits of Digital India Programme:

Digital India programme is the beginning of digital revolution. It is a big initiative to empower people of the country. Main benefits of this programme are-

1. The digital India mission would make all the government services available to people of country through common service delivery outlets. This would lead to inclusive growth by enabling access to education, healthcare and government services to all the citizens of the country. People can get better advice on health services. Those who can't afford school/ colleges can get chance to online education. There would be more transparency as all the data would be made online and would be accessible to citizens of the country. E-Governance will help in reducing corruption and getting things done quickly.
2. Digital locker facility will help citizen to digitally store their important documents like Pan card, passport, mark sheets etc. 1st July 2015 launched this Digi Locker scheme. As of mid 2026 Digi locker has served over 55 crore (550 million) registered users across India.
3. It will help in getting things done easily. For example, when we need to open an account, we will give official details of our digital locker, where they can verify our documents. By this we can save time and the pain of standing in long queues for getting our documents would be reduced. It will help in decreasing documentation and reducing paper work. Digital India mission is away for cashless transactions. Nearly 40 times increase in transactions on UPI since November, 2016 and 128 million downloads and active user of BHIM and More than 7 to 8 million transactions on BHIM per day in mid 2026. It can help small businesses. People can use online tools to expand their business.
4. It can play a key role in GDP growth. According to analyst the digital India could boost GDP up to \$4.58 trillion in 2027. According to World Bank report a 10% increase in mobile and broadband penetration increases per capita GDP by 0.81% and 1.31% respectively in developing countries. The programme would generate huge number of jobs in IT, electronics and telecommunication sector directly or indirectly.

Skills Requires for Digital Economy:

Human Skills apply social, creative and critical intelligence. These skills –critical thinking, creativity, communication, analytical skills, collaboration, and relationship building – appear on many lists of sought-after 'Soft Skills' and are still in high demand across the digitally intensive economy. Skills relate both to the effective use of new technologies and the ability to work in new working environments.

Digital Infrastructures and Their Future Demand:

Goldman Sachs predicts that India - comprising 15% of the world population, with a growth rate of 7 to 8%, could be the second largest economy by 2030. India's new leadership considers the digital economy as a major growth enabler. Digital infrastructure as a core tool to every Indian, smart e-governance, on demand digital services and digital empowerment of citizens. New policies at national and international levels needed to build an inclusive digital economy. Technology is not deterministic. It creates both: opportunities and challenges. The global nature of the digital economy

will require close dialogue with other stakeholders, Academia, Private Sector, Tech community Civil Society and government to shape the digital economy.

Policy Making:

Policy makers need to make choices that can help reverse the trend towards widening inequalities and power imbalances, Policy areas that need particular attention Strengthening the readiness of developing countries to engage in and benefit from e-commerce and the digital economy. Labour market, skills and social protection policies needed. Digital entrepreneurship and innovation policies equal domestic opportunities, including for women. Intellectual property policies must be promoted in the digital economy. Development cooperation with more attention to the digital dimension with Competition policies for the digital era and Taxation of digital platforms.

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